

Qualitative Study on Integration of Pragmatic Teaching Approach at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria: A Systematic Review

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Abstract

It is a common scenario nowadays to see university graduates remain jobless, even though some of them graduate with first- and second-class honours, respectively. This gets one wondering what could be the cause; could it be the fault of the government who has not made enough jobs available, the teachers who have not taught the students effectively by using the right methods thereby not equipping them enough to handle real life situations, the school curriculum that is not properly structured or (the unavailability of teaching aids) thereby not matching theory with practice? The researcher therefore provides answers to the following questions; what are the crisis of education according to pragmatism? What should be the nature of curriculum? What is pragmatic education? How does it assist learners to learn? what are the problems associated with pragmatic education? And what are the difficulties on the part of the students that is not making this part of education work? The study adopted philosophical methods of analysis and prescription. It was recommended among others that the pragmatic teaching methods should be used in our universities as this will help students balance theory with practice and for better understand of subject matter.

Keywords: Pragmatism, Nigerian Education, Pragmatic Education, Curriculum

Introduction

The problem surrounding university graduates in Nigeria not being able to apply what they have learnt in school into real life situation and thereby making a living from it is alarming and has been a lot of concern to the philosophers of education, school administrators, policy formulators, parents, teachers and the students as well. Plato an idealist believes that teachers should be at the centre of teaching activities in the school while Rousseau, an advocate of child centered education is of the view that students should be given consideration and allowed to contribute their ideas during classroom activities. Pragmatists strike a balance between the two positions, they believe that teaching should pave way for both the teacher and the students to take active participation in the teaching and learning process as this would greatly assist the students gain deeper and practical knowledge/experience of their areas of specialization and it was concluded amongst others that the pragmatic method of teaching should be adopted in our universities. The philosophical method of enquiry was used.

The term metaphysics literally means 'beyond the physical'. This area of philosophy focuses on the nature of reality. Metaphysics attempts to find unity across the domains of experiences and thoughts. At the metaphysical level, there are four broad philosophical schools of thought that apply to education today. They are; idealism, realism, pragmatism (sometime called

experientialism) and existentialism. Each will be explained, these four general frameworks provide the root or base from which the various educational philosophies are derived.

Two of these general or world philosophies, idealism and realism are derived from the ancient Greek philosophers, Plato and Aristotle. Two more contemporary; pragmatism and existentialism. However, educators who share one of these distinct sets of beliefs about the nature of reality presently apply each of these world philosophies in successful classrooms activities. Let me explain these metaphysical schools of thought briefly;

It is common nowadays for one to graduate from the university and remain jobless. Gone are the days when jobs were readily available for university graduates. Getting employed by government has now become just a dream that becomes a reality only to the 'well connected' individuals in society. This is troubling. Sometimes, the so called university graduate cannot effectively and confidently defend his certificate, other times his services are not relevant or even needed in his society. What could be the problem? Some of these graduates would say their certificates cannot be used to get jobs as what they have learnt from school or their areas of expertise are not relevant or are not useful for work in their immediate society. This has made some of these young ones delve into criminal activities just to 'make ends meet'. This is indeed worrisome.

Aim and Objectives of Tertiary Education in Nigeria

Creation of new values:

Pragmatists have no fixed aims or goals of education. According to Ross, 'The general educational aim of the pragmatist is just the creation of new values.' So, the main task of the educator is to put the educed into a position of developing value of himself.

Activity and Experience:

For the creation of new values, activity and experience are essential. Education should therefore provide physical, intellectual, moral and aesthetic activities as the media for the creation of values.

Personal and Social Adjustment:

All these aspects are developed not for their own sake, but for meeting the individual and social needs of man. So the main aim of education is 'to direct the impulses, interests and abilities towards the satisfaction of the need felt child in the environment.

Reconstruction of experience:

Then, as every individual is required to solve many diverse problems in his life, the aim of education should also be the formulation and cultivation of a dynamic, adoptable, resourceful, and enterprising mind. It is with such a mind that original and creative thinking is possible which will enable a person to cope successfully with the varied situations of life. Pragmatism emphasizes adaptation to environment, construction and re-construction of experience and development of capacity to control the environment.

All Round Development:

All round development of the individual is also important aim of education. The individual develops physically, mentally, socially, morally, and aesthetically.

Methodology

The study adopted philosophical methods of analysis and prescription. Thus, the study looked at available literature to analyze the views of relevant authorities with the aim of prescribing relevant suggestions.

Theoretical perspectives to the problem

Idealism perspectives to the problem of integration of pragmatic education in Nigeria:

Idealism is a philosophical approach that has as its central tenet that ideas are the only true reality, the only thing worth knowing. In a search for truth, beauty and justice that is enduring and everlasting, the focus is on conscious reasoning in the mind. Plato, father of idealism, believed that there are two world; the spiritual or mental world which is eternal, permanent, orderly, regular and universal. There is also the world of appearance, the world experienced through sight, touch, smell, taste, and sound, that is changing, imperfect, and disorderly. This division is often referred to as the duality of mind and body. To understand truth, one must pursue knowledge and identify with the absolute mind.

In idealism, the aim of education is to discover and develop each individual's abilities and full moral excellence in order to better serve society. The curricular emphasis is subject matter of mind, literature, history, philosophy and religion. Teaching methods focus on handling ideas through lecture, discussion, and Socratic dialogue (a method of teaching that uses questioning to help students discover and clarify knowledge). Character is built through imitating examples and here (introduction ends here).

Realism perspectives to the problem of integration of pragmatic education in Nigeria:

Realists believe that reality exists independent of the human mind. The ultimate reality is the world of objects. The focus is on the object/body. Aristotle, a student of Plato who broke with his mentor's idealist philosophy is called the father of both realism and scientific method. In this metaphysical view, the aim is to understand objective reality through 'the diligent and unsparing scrutiny of all observable data'. Aristotle believed that to understand an object, its ultimate form had to be understood, which does not change. For example, a rose exists whether or not a person is aware of it.

The realist curriculum emphasizes the subject matter of the physical world, particularly science and mathematics. The teacher organizes and presents content systematically within a discipline, demonstrating use of criteria in making decisions. Teaching methods focus on mastery of facts and basic skills through demonstration and recitation. Students must also demonstrate the ability to think critically and scientifically, using observation and experimentation. Curriculum should be scientifically approaches, standardized, and distinct discipline base. Character is developed through training in the rules of conduct. Just as people say experience is the best teacher for pragmatists.

Pragmatism (Experientialism) perspectives to the problem of integration of pragmatic education in Nigeria:

For pragmatists only thing that are experienced or observed are real. In the late 19th century, American philosophy, the focus is on the reality of experience. Unlike the realists and rationalists, pragmatists believe that reality is constantly changing and that we learn best through applying our experiences and thoughts to problems as they arise. The universe is dynamic and evolving, a 'becoming' view of the world. There is no absolute and unchanging truth, but rather, truth is what works. Pragmatism is derived from the teachings of Charles Sanders Peirce (1839-1914), who believed that thought must produce action rather than longer in the mind and lead to indecisiveness.

John Dewey (1859-1952) applied pragmatists, philosophy in his progressive approaches. He believed that learners must adapt to each other and to their environment. Schools should emphasize that subjects should emphasize the subject matter of social experience. All learning is dependent on the content of place, time, and circumstance.

For pragmatists, teaching methods focus on hand on problem solving, experimenting and projects often having students work in groups. Curriculum should bring the discipline together to focus on solving problems in an interdisciplinary way. Rather than passing down organized bodies of knowledge to new learners, pragmatists believe that learners should apply their knowledge to real situations through experimental enquiry. This prepares students for citizenship, daily living and future careers.

Existentialism perspectives to the problem of integration of pragmatic education in Nigeria:

The nature of reality for existentialists is subjective, and lies within the individual. The physical world has no inherent meaning outside of human existence. Individual choice and individual standards are central. Existence comes before any definition of what we are. We define ourselves in relationships to that existence by the choices we make. We should not accept any one else's predetermined philosophical system; rather, we must take responsibility for deciding who we are. The focus is on freedom, the development of lives. Soren Kierkegaard (1813-1855), a Danish minister and philosopher, is considered to be the founder of existentialism. His was a Christian orientation. Another group of existentialists, largely European, believes that we must recognize the tinitners of our les-bodies of our lives n this small and fragile planet with other than believing in salvation through God. Existentialists have focused more on human quest for personal meaning. Value clarification is an outgrowth of this movement.

Related to education, the subject matter of existentialist classrooms should be a matter of personal choice. Teachers view the individual as an entity within a social context in which the learner must confront others' view to clarify his or her own. Character development emphasizes individual responsibility for decisions. Real answers come from within the individual, not from outside authority. Examining life through authentic thinking involves students in genuine learning experiences. Existentialists are opposed to thinking about students as objects to be measured, tracked, or standardized. Such educators want the educational experience to focus on creating opportunities from self-direction and self-actualization. They start with the student, rather than on curriculum content.

The Features/ Principles of Pragmatic Education integration in tertiary level of education in Nigeria

No ultimate values:

The main principle of pragmatic philosophy is that man creates his own values during the course f activity. There are no fixed values for all times too come. Even truths are man-made products. There is nothing like absolute truths.

According to pragmatism

'Whatever fulfils man's purpose and desires and develops his life is true. Truth is what which gives satisfactory results when put into practice'.

Emphasis on experimentation:

Pragmatism lays a special stress on the value of experimentation. It stands for testing every statement by finding out its practical implications. If these implications are desirable, the statement is accepted, otherwise rejected. Man is always carrying out various experiments in his life. But no judgment is possible before an experiment is tested by experience

Belief in practical philosophy:

Pragmatism believes that philosophy is not simply wisdom of the past. True philosophy is one that helps in the solution of practical problems of life. John Dewey says, 'Philosophy in order to be philosophy should have meaning and utility in the solution of human problems. It should be practical and useful in the solution of human problems and in influencing the conduct of life and not a passive enquiry or contemplation'.

Human Development According to Environment

Pragmatism believes that growth of human personality takes place because of interaction with environment. Man tries to adjust himself to his environment and this result in his growth. During the process of adjustment man not only adopts himself to his environment but he also tries to mould the environment according to his needs, purpose and desires.

Faith in Democracy:

Pragmatism has deep faith in democracy. It is only through democracy that an individual can realize the maximum development of his personality. Individual development leads to the development of society.

Revolt against Traditionalism:

Pragmatism believes that reality is in the making. Truth is that which works in practical situation. Whatever fulfills one's purpose and develops his life, is true. So it is a revolt against traditionalism and absolutism.

Emphasis on the Principle of Unity:

Pragmatism is a utilitarian philosophy which holds that the reality of a principle lies in its utility. Any idea or thing which is useful to us is proper and right in case, it is of no use. In other words, only those ideas and things are true which have a utility for man. In the words of William James, 'it is true because it is useful'.

Importance of man power:

Pragmatism emphasizes on the power of man to a great extent. By virtues of this power, a man can create an environment useful, beneficial and conducive to his own development and welfare of society.

Faith is flexibility:

Pragmatism believes that nothing is fixed and final in this world. Everything grows, changes and develops. In other words, the world is changing and everything is under the process of change. Human life is also changing.

Reality still in the making:

To pragmatists future is more helpful and bright in comparison with the present. The world is still in the process of formation and development. Man is to aid this process of information to such an extent that all the needs and requirements of human beings are fully satisfied. In this sense pragmatic attitude is optimistic, developing and progressive.

Importance of Activity:

Pragmatism lays great emphasis on activity rather than on ideas. Pragmatists hold the view that ideas are born out of activities. Man is an active being. Thus, the greatest contribution of pragmatism to education is the principle of "learning by doing".

Pragmatism and Curriculum Implementation at tertiary level of education in Nigeria:

The aims of education are reflected in the curriculum. The pragmatic aims can only be reflected in a pragmatic curriculum. The curriculum should be framed on the basis of certain basic principles. These are utility, interest, experience and integration. Practical utility is the watchword of pragmatism.

Hence, those subjects which have utility to the students should be included in the curriculum. The subjects which carry occupational or vocational utility should fund a place in the curriculum. Language, hygiene, history, geography, physics, mathematics, sciences, domestic science, agriculture, computer science, entrepreneurial etc. should be incorporated in the curriculum. While deciding the subjects of curriculum, the nature of the child, his tendencies, interests' impulses at the various stages of his growth and multiple activities of daily life should be taken into consideration. It is important that subjects like psychology and sociology- which deals with human behaviour, should be included in the curriculum also.

Pragmatists advocate that the pupils should not be taught dead facts and theories because these may not help them to solve the problems of life. The subjects which help to solve the practical problems of life should be included in the school curriculums particularly at the elementary stage. The pragmatic aim of education is to prepare the child for a successful and well-adjusted life. He must be fully adjusted to his environment. Learners should learn only those skills which are useful to them in practical life. With this end in view, the elementary school curriculum should include subjects like reading, writing, anthemic, nature study, handwork and drawing. According to pragmatism, all education is 'learning by doing', so, it must be based on the child's experience as well as occupations and activities. Besides the school subjects, free, purposive, and socialized

activities should be in the curriculum. The pragmatists do not allow the inclusion of cultural activities in the curriculum, because they think these activities have no practical value.

Pragmatism and Method of Teaching at tertiary level of education in Nigeria:

The principle of philosophy of pragmatic method of teaching is practical utility. The child is the central figure in this method. Pragmatic method is an activity-based method. Pragmatic education means preparation for practical life. The child should know the act of successful tackling of practical problems and real situations of life. Pragmatic method is thus a problem-solving method. The child has to be placed in real situation which he has to tackle. The pragmatists are not interested in lectures of theoretical exposition. They want the children to do something, action rather than contemplation figures prominently, in pragmatic education. Learning by doing is the great maxim of pragmatic education. Learning by doing makes a person creative, confident and cooperative. The pragmatic method is socialistic in nature. He should learn to fulfill the purpose of his life. The method employed by the pragmatist teacher is experimental. The pupil is required to discover the truth for himself.

The business of the teacher, therefore is to teach his pupil to do rather than to know, to discover for themselves rather than to collect dry information. The teacher is required to suggest and prompt only. The teacher suggests problems, indicates the lines of active solution and then leaves the students to experiment for themselves. Pragmatic education is thus, auto-education or self-education. Pragmatic method is a project method which is of American origin. The pragmatist does not however fix up his methods once and for all. His methods are dynamic, varying from time to time and class to class. If the essentials of teacher- learning situations are present the method will automatically follow.

Findings

From this study, it was discovered that the pragmatic method of teacher and learning is very effective. It encourages the students to relate with their environment or society and carry out research, experiments for themselves thereby relating theory with / to practice for deeper and wider understanding.

Conclusion

Integration of Pragmatic Teaching Approach at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria enhances acquisition of skills and improves productivity among the students and society at large

Recommendation

1. Students of universities should be given the opportunity to do more of practical work not just theory as this will help them gain deeper knowledge and understanding of their subject area. Thereby gain skills that would help them meet societal needs and be useful to themselves.
2. Every university should have an Entrepreneurship Development Center where every university student should register and learn at least a skill that will be useful to them upon graduation from school.
3. Government should walk hand in hand with other university authorities stakeholders to make this a reality by making funds available for such centres to be adequately equipped.
4. The pragmatic teaching methods should be used in our universities as this will help students balance theory with practice and for better understanding of subject matter.

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